
A Study on the Quality of Content in Higher Education in India

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Abstract

The content in the Higher Education System in India has to be improved upon still from the levels of what it is today. The authorities such as UGC are making several regulations that should improve the quality of content in Higher Education in India. Still there are many other areas which need to be taken into consideration for the improvement in quality of higher education in India. The present-day environment is not conducive to achieve growth as desired. The modern student society is a prey to the social networks and media that has tremendous influence on their life as a student. This paper aims to unravel some of the aspects which are plausible causes, and among which lack of Mentoring of the students takes the prime seat. The study also makes an attempt to find if the intellectual and emotional quotients (IQ & EQ) of the students are coming down or impaired and if the faculty of thinking itself is not being put to use by the students. The Study concludes that scientific and effective mentoring does have a positive impact on the student behaviour, student absenteeism, and other problems posed by the students to the teachers and the institution. Further the steps taken to further the quality has to be implemented by all the stakeholders and there cannot be compromise by any of them. India has still hopes on its higher education system to deliver world-class citizens to the society in the future.

Keywords: Mentoring; Emotional Quotient; Intelligent Quotient; academics

INTRODUCTION

The purpose of Education has mainly one reason. It has to improve the quality of the Man. Only Education must speed up the momentum of the economic growth of the country and its investment decisions and is one of the keys to a better quality of life and improved Human Development Index (HDI), (Agarwal, 2015). India has the reputation of being the oldest civilization in the world and the founder of high quality education system. India was the first country to establish the first International University at Takshasila which flourished from 600 BC to 500 AD, in the kingdom of Gandhar. (NW India, and today's Pakistan). It had

students from Babylon, Greece, Syria, and China. (Quality Enhancement in Higher Education Institutions in India: Challenges Ahead (2016) by Katta Rama Mohana Rao and Chandra Sekhar Patro). The Nalanda ruins reveal through their architectural components the holistic nature of knowledge that was sought and imparted at this University. It suggests a seamless co-existence between nature and man and between living and learning. The great universities of the western world came into being, when Nalanda ceased to exist, (destroyed by invaders close to the end of the 12th century) except OXFORD, BOLOGNA & Al Azhar.

Today's Scenario in India

Statistics gleaned from UGC Website on the institutions or Universities in India promoting Higher Education

• Central Universities	47
• State Universities	384
• Deemed to be Universities	123
• State Private Universities	<u>296</u>
Total of all universities	<u>850</u>
• <u>Fake Universities</u>	24

(figures as on 29-06-2017; 06-10-2017; April 2018 from UGC website)

UGC Sponsored 8 studies - entitled "Higher Education in India-Issues Related to Expansion, Inclusiveness, Quality and Finance". While mentioning an enrolment rate about 11%, the issue of quality in education was also addressed through several initiatives. The issues related to the teachers formed the main component of the studies on the quality of higher education.

Determinants of Quality in Universities, (as per UGC)

- Age of the University
- Number of departments in the university
- Number of teachers in each department of the university
- Proportion of the filled up teaching positions
- Proportion of teachers with PhD as highest qualification

It is imperative that the quality of the universities need to be upgraded constantly, which in turn, will help achieve quality standards across all the institutions of learning, which is the greatest challenge today in India.

UGC mentions in its website that there are:

- Ø 23 state universities under group C and
- Ø 67 state universities under group B

which all need to upgrade in quality.

NAAC for QUALITY - Quality of Higher Education in India

The National Assessment and Accreditation Council (NAAC) was established in 1994 to take up the responsibility of setting standards for Higher Educational Institutions in India. It is an External Quality Assurance (EQA) agency.

Out of 164 universities, only 128 universities have got themselves accredited by the National Assessment and Accreditation Council (NAAC) and only 32 percent of them could get A or above level of rating while another 52 percent of them could manage with B or above grade.

The remaining 16% universities fall in group 3 having obtained grades C and above. Till recently, not many institutions have approached NAAC for accreditation. But not enough empirical evidence is available to establish that those institutions that have obtained NAAC certification have undergone change in the quality of education. Lot of study have to be done on the role, nature and adequacy of these Quality Assurance agencies.

Table Showing NAAC Ratings

Quality Status of Universities

Indicators	Number
Total Number of Universities	369
Number of Universities under UGC Purview	317
Number of Universities eligible to receive UGC grants	164
Universities with infrastructure deficiencies & not eligible to receive UGC grants though in its purview	153
Universities accredited by NAAC of which Rated as	128
• A++, A+, A (Group 1)	32%
• B++, B+, B (Group 2)	52%
• C++, C+, C (Group 3)	16%

The following degree awarding Institutions in India.

1. Central University - A university established or incorporated by a Central Act.
2. State University - A university established or incorporated by a Provincial Act or by a State Act.
3. Open University - A University which imparts education exclusively through distance education in any branch or branches of knowledge.
4. Private University - A university established through a State/ Central Act by a sponsoring

body viz. a Society registered under the Societies Registration Act 1860, or any other corresponding law for the time being in force in a State or a Public Trust or a Company registered under Section 25 of the Companies Act, 1956.

5. Deemed University - An Institution Deemed to be University commonly known as Deemed University refers to a high-performing institute, which has been so declared by Central Government under Section 3 of the University Grants Commission (UGC) Act, 1956.
6. Institute of National Importance - An Institution established by Act of Parliament and declared as Institution of National Importance such as All Indian Institute of Technology (IIT), National Institute of Technology (NIT).
7. Institute Under State Legislature Act - An institution established or incorporated by a State Legislature Act such as Nizam's Institute of Medical Sciences, Hyderabad; Sri Venkateswara Institute of Medical Sciences, Tirupati; Shree-Kashmir Institute of Medical Sciences, Srinagar; Indira Gandhi Institute of Medical Sciences, Patna; Sanjay Gandhi Post Graduate Institute of Medical Sciences, Lucknow.
8. Other Institute – An institution not falling in any of the above category but established through State/ Central Act and are empowered to award degrees e.g. National Institute of Fashion Technology established through an Act of Parliament.

Possible Solutions to achieve quality of content in Higher Education

Through this paper some viable suggestive solutions for meeting the Challenges in the Quality Of Higher Education in India are provided below.

1. At the Grassroots improving the Quality of Content

1. Vigorous use of Information Technology and Communications Technology
2. Curriculum should be really relevant to Modern Corporate Needs
3. Minimum number of Case Studies in all subjects to be made mandatory

4. Real Corporate Environment Exposure to be provided to all students.
5. Encourage Experiential Learning at each stage.
6. Promote ORIGINAL RESEARCH among faculties and students
7. Develop INNOVATIVE IDEAS among students and faculties

2. Making of the Syllabi

1. Frequency of revision of syllabi to be done at least once in 2 years
2. Tailored to General Corporate Needs at the time of drafting the syllabi
(basic computer skills, basic English, basic soft skills have become common)
3. Case studies from real life and corporate cases for each subject
4. Approval of syllabi by an Expert Committee comprising Deans, Subject specialists from Outside, Industry captains, socialists from across various domains

3. Use of Advanced IT and CT

1. Fully Wi-fi enabled campus with enough speed and band-width has to be insisted upon.
2. Judicious use of smart-phones and tablets by students for educational classroom sessions
3. Encourage students to read e-newspapers, e-journals, e-publications etc.
4. Using Advanced Excel for real business scenarios
5. Each faculty and student should have blogs to their credit.

4. Mentoring and Coaching of Students towards a Goal

1. Each subject should be focused on case studies pertinent to it.
2. A mentor-mentee relationship should start from Academic portals
3. Mentoring and Coaching should complement the Teaching Plans

5. Take into account Modern Corporate Needs

- Train and develop the power and skill of Decision-Making
- Train on Risk-taking with adequate precautions
- Intrapreneurship qualities of students to be developed using suitable programs
- The approach should be 'more potential Leaders and not workers are needed'
- Switch from Individual as a student to Individual as a Professional Corporate should happen in a short period of time

CONCLUSION

Apart from the lofty objective of improving the quality of life by improving the quality of the content of Higher Education, there is also one more objective which demands attention today. That is 'what Modern Corporate Needs are today'? It depends on the quality of the higher education and its updated contents.

Modern Business/Corporate need **QUICK L T P s**

- Quick Learners
- Quick Thinkers
- Quick Performers/Achievers

All these attempts of Research on Quality in Higher Education and the relevant efforts are made possibly for the benefit of the STUDENT or the Institution or the Parents or for the Teachers. While it may be 'Yes' for all the above, ultimately it is for the society at large and for human growth and betterment in the quality of life of human beings. But the paradox still remains that not many people are really interested in 'Quality' in whatever aspect of life, and higher education is too vital to be put in that category, especially in today's fiercely competitive world.

Scope for further Research

There is ample scope for further research on this aspect of Quality of content in Higher Education. The reason is not far to seek. More life-style changes, more inventions, innovations and man's desire to add to his comforts will always keep the demand for research alive in this domain.
